

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20713839
published on [Zenodo](#)

Status: 16 June 2026

Global Framework Data for a Feasibility Stress Test of Paris-Compatible National Targets

Global Framework Data, Structural Limits, and Residual Mitigation Gaps

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1 Introduction¹

This paper seeks to identify global framework data² that would allow for national territorial emission reduction targets that are as realistic as possible and, in aggregate, compatible with the Paris Agreement. A key result is that, even under this deliberately feasibility-oriented framework, a remaining mitigation gap persists.

The national emission targets are based on national CO₂ budgets derived from a remaining global CO₂ budget. A weighted distribution key is used, which includes the country's share of the global population and global emissions in 2019.

The institutional framework (e.g., top-down or bottom-up approaches) within which this global framework data could be applied is not discussed in this paper.

Regarding the methodology (Extended Smooth Pathway Model, ESPM³), including the data basis used and the corresponding limitations, explicit reference is made [to](#) (Sargl, et al., 2026).⁴ That study presents results across a wide range of global framework data for the six largest emitters.

¹ For simplicity, the subscript 2 in CO₂ is omitted.

² The term “global framework data” is used in this paper as a concise umbrella term for the empirical input data and framework choices required to operationalize the ESPM. These framework choices are made transparent and should not be understood as purely empirical data or as scientifically predetermined values.

³ Here is a brief description of the ESPM: <https://espm-short.climate-calculator.info>.

⁴ Footnotes accompanying the individual global framework data provide brief explanations of the ESPM. However, reading the introductory chapters [in](#) (Sargl, et al., 2026) is recommended.

2 Global framework data⁵

This chapter specifies the global framework choices used in the ESPM to determine national emission targets. It first specifies the remaining global CO₂ budget and then explains the adjustments required to derive the budget that can be allocated to countries in the present analysis (see Table 1 in Chapter 3). In doing so, maximum use is made of the available leeway to arrive at national targets that are as realistic as possible overall.

With regard to the following framework choices, it should be noted that the author is an economist and does not claim specific expertise in the natural sciences. Feedback from experts with specific expertise in the relevant natural-science fields is particularly welcome.

2.1 Global CO₂ budget

This paper uses a [global CO₂ budget](#) of 680 Gt for the period 2020–2100.

Reason:

680 Gt corresponds to an 83% probability of limiting global warming to below 1.88 °C and can therefore be interpreted as an upper-bound case of compatibility with the Paris Agreement’s objective of staying **well** below 2 °C (cf. Wolfsteiner, 2026).⁶

The chosen global CO₂ budget should therefore be understood as an upper-bound interpretation of Paris compatibility under real-world political and economic constraints.

2.2 Adjustments to the allocable global CO₂ budget

The global CO₂ budget specified above cannot be allocated directly to countries without further adjustments, because the country-level emissions data used in this paper do not cover all relevant global CO₂ sources and sinks. Based on the adjustments described in the following subsections — a LUC budget of 0 Gt, a budget of 22 Gt reserved for international shipping and aviation (ISA), and a global cement carbonation sink (CeCS) of 40 Gt — the allocable global CO₂ budget used for the

⁵ **Results based on alternative global framework data:**

Results for the **six largest emitters** across a wide range of global framework data are presented [in](#) (Sargl, et al., 2026).

A web application providing **national CO₂ budgets for all countries** based on specified global framework data: <https://national-budgets.climate-calculator.info>. This application shows the results based on a linear emissions path.

Emission pathways consistent with a specified budget can be calculated using RM Scenario Types via: <https://paths.climate-calculator.info>. The emission pathways can also reflect net negative emissions and thus a **temporary volume overshoot**.

An **overview** of all available **tools** is provided at: <https://climate-calculator.info>.

⁶ The CO₂ budget corresponding to 1.88 °C was determined by linear interpolation.

country-level allocation in this paper amounts to 698 Gt ($680 - 0 - (+22) - (-40)$). These adjustments are treated at the global level because the corresponding sources and sinks are not included in the territorial country-level emissions data applied in this framework (EDGAR, 2025).

2.2.1 Land-use change CO₂ emissions (LUC)⁷

The global LUC (land-use change) budget for 2020–2100 is assumed to be **zero**.

Reason:

In the author's view, offsetting today's positive global LUC emissions with future negative emissions is already a major challenge. Consequently, a negative LUC budget is regarded as implausible.

2.2.2 International shipping and aviation (ISA)

A global budget of 22 Gt is reserved for CO₂ emissions from international shipping and aviation (ISA) for the period 2020–2100.

Reason:

The value of 22 Gt is based on the current order of magnitude of ISA emissions as a share of global CO₂ emissions and is applied as a pragmatic framework assumption.

2.2.3 Cement carbonation sink (CeCS)

A global cement carbonation sink (CeCS) of 40 Gt for the period 2020–2100 is taken into account.

Reason:

Cement production causes CO₂ emissions, but cement-based materials also absorb CO₂ from the atmosphere over time through carbonation. The Global Carbon Project estimates the cement carbonation sink at around -0.8 GtCO₂ in 2019 (GCP, 2025). If this annual 2019 sink were extrapolated linearly over the period 2020–2100, the resulting cumulative sink would be substantially above 40 GtCO₂. The value used here is therefore a conservative framework assumption: it recognizes CeCS as a relevant global sink, while avoiding reliance on an optimistic long-term projection.

⁷ Since the country data used does not include LUC emissions, a LUC budget is reserved at global level. A detailed discussion of the accounting logic underlying this assumption is provided [in](#) (Sargl, et al., 2026) and is not repeated here.

2.3 Potential for net negative emissions (overshoot)⁸

A potential for annual net negative emissions of **-2%** of emissions in 2019 is assumed (minimum value of the emission pathway).⁹

Reason:

This results in an overshoot of the same order of magnitude as the 2019 emissions (see temporary overshoot in Table 1).

In the author's view, this already represents a major challenge.

Notes:

- The period during which the temperature target is temporarily exceeded should be as short as possible in order to **minimize the resulting damage**.
- An overshoot increases the risk of exceeding **tipping points** in the climate system, meaning that the original temperature limit can no longer be achieved, even though the corresponding budget is being adhered to.
- Negative CO₂ emissions must be generated **in addition** to those required to offset unavoidable greenhouse gas emissions in order to achieve climate neutrality.

The assumed level of net negative emissions should therefore not be interpreted as a target, but as a hard upper bound that already implies significant climatic and socio-economic risk.

2.4 Scenario type used for emission pathways¹⁰

The **RM-4-quadr** scenario type was used, which assumes an initially slow increase in ambition as reflected in annual change rates (cf. Figure 2).¹¹

Reason:

No rapid increase in ambition is expected in the first few years.

⁸ The RM Scenario Types used in ESPM to determine emission pathways can also be used to map temporary overshoots of the specified budget if a negative value is specified as the minimum emission value.

⁹ Net negative CO₂ emissions refer to a period in which CO₂ removals exceed remaining positive CO₂ emissions, so that the net CO₂ balance becomes negative.

¹⁰ The RM Scenario Types offer the possibility to determine emission pathways that comply with a specified CO₂ budget and can also map an overshoot. The scenario types differ mainly in the course of the annual rates of change. See also the excursus on RM Scenario Types [in](#) (Sargl, et al., 2026). Here is a brief description: <https://rm-scenario-types.climate-calculator.info>. This web application illustrates the different types of scenarios: <https://paths.climate-calculator.info>.

The actual emissions available at the time of calculation are taken into account in the results in Table 1.

¹¹ The actual rate from 2024 is used as the starting rate of change for 2025. This is likely to be a strong indicator of the rates of change in the following years in reality.

The resulting very high annual reduction rates in later years are considered reasonable, responsible, and achievable if national climate policies demonstrate a high degree of credibility, for example through binding emissions caps in emissions trading systems.

2.5 Weighting of the population in the allocation of a global CO₂ budget¹²

The population is weighted at 12%.

Reason:

This weighting is ultimately based on an assessment of the resulting outcomes. In doing so, the author aimed to choose the highest possible weighting for the population, while ensuring that the results remain politically feasible and economically reasonable. This approach already accounts for some transfer of budgets and additional negative emissions (see Chapters 5.3 and 5.4).

From a strictly fairness-based perspective, there is much to be said for a weighting of 100%. However, this would lead to politically unfeasible results in industrialized countries, including China, and would have an excessively strong impact on the global economy and thus on global welfare, which is a prerequisite for a successful climate transformation and positive economic development in the Global South as well.

Another argument in favor of a weighting of 12% is that in the Regensburg Model, with converging per capita emissions at a convergence level of 0.5 t, an implicit weighting of the population of a similar magnitude results (cf. Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2024).¹³ However, here too, the convergence level of 0.5 t is ultimately based on an assessment of what is considered realistic.

A population weighting of 12% is ultimately based on the author's subjective assessment of what is realistic, reasonable, and still ethically justifiable.

In the author's assessment, higher population weights would, under real-world political and economic constraints, not increase global equity in practice but instead increase the probability of collective failure.

Beyond population weighting, additional allocation criteria are frequently proposed, most notably historical responsibility and indicators of economic capability such as GDP per capita. While such criteria are well grounded from normative and ethical perspectives, their inclusion does not, in the

¹² A weighted distribution key is used to derive a national CO₂ budget from a global CO₂ budget, which includes a country's share of the global population and global emissions in 2019. Once the weighting of the population has been determined, the weighting of emissions is also determined. For the fundamental question of an allocation key, see the relevant excursus [in](#) (Sargl, et al., 2026).

¹³ Here is a simplified web application for the Regensburg Model: <https://rm.climate-calculator.info>.

author's assessment, lead to more realistic overall outcomes when evaluated from a global feasibility perspective. For a detailed discussion, see the relevant excursus [in](#) (Sargl, et al., 2026).

2.6 Interpretation of global framework data

The global framework data selected in this paper should not be interpreted as normative targets or as an ethically optimal allocation of remaining global CO₂ budgets. Rather, they define a set of boundary conditions under which territorially defined national emission pathways are assessed for their collective compatibility with the Paris Agreement **under real-world political, economic, and technological constraints**.

The chosen framework data combine three different elements:

- (i) **Physical and climatological constraints**, primarily the remaining global CO₂ budget and limits to temporary temperature overshoot, which are derived from IPCC-based assessments;
- (ii) **Assumptions on political and economic feasibility**, such as the scenario type, achievable rates of emission reduction, and the treatment of net negative emissions;
- (iii) **Deliberately conservative risk assumptions**, in particular regarding land-use change (LUC) emissions and the limited availability of net negative CO₂ emissions.

While some core input data and physical relationships draw on IPCC-based assessments and other scientific sources, several elements of the global framework data necessarily involve fact-based judgment calls rather than scientifically predetermined values. In addition, explicitly normative choices are unavoidable, most notably in the weighting of population in the allocation key. These judgment calls and value choices are explicitly stated and are not presented as objective facts or scientific consensus.

The framework data are therefore not intended to represent a “best-case” or a “most ambitious feasible” pathway. Instead, they are designed to explore whether **a set of globally consistent national targets remains attainable at all** when overly optimistic assumptions are avoided.

Where fact-based judgment calls and explicit value choices are unavoidable — most notably in assumptions on achievable net negative emissions and in the weighting of population in the allocation of national budgets — these choices are based on the author's assessment of what can be considered politically plausible and economically sustainable at the global level. Higher population weightings or more optimistic assumptions on negative emissions would improve results for individual countries but would, in the author's assessment, significantly increase the risk of collective failure to meet the temperature objective of the Paris Agreement.

In this sense, the global framework data used here should be understood as a **stress test for the feasibility of Paris-compatible national targets**, rather than as a prescriptive statement on fairness or responsibility.

Accordingly, the selected framework data should be understood as a transparent, judgment-based interpretation of realistic global boundary conditions. Different authors may arrive at different assessments; however, more optimistic assumptions would, in the author's view, systematically underestimate the risks of overshoot, political non-compliance, and delayed mitigation.

3 Results for the 35 countries with the highest resulting CO2 budgets¹⁴

global CO2 budget 2020–2100 in Gt		680				minimum annual emissions				-2%	
weighting population		12%				LUC 0 Gt		ISA 3.3%		CeCS -40 Gt	
reference values (paths: RM-4-quadr)						budget 2020–2100 in Gt	share of global budget	temporary overshoot in Gt	year emissions neutrality	emissions 2019 in Gt	share of global emissions
target year:	2030	2030	2035	2040							
reference year → country ↓	1990	2019									
1	China	432%	9%	-26%	-76%	213.2	30.5%	12.72	2047	11.81	32.2%
2	United States	-9%	-9%	-26%	-59%	86.7	12.4%	4.90	2051	4.97	13.5%
3	India	530%	48%	7%	-72%	57.6	8.2%	2.82	2045	2.55	7.0%
4	EU27	-43%	-25%	-36%	-51%	53.5	7.7%	2.21	2062	2.91	7.9%
5	Russia	-10%	17%	-28%	-87%	32.7	4.7%	2.09	2044	1.86	5.1%
6	Japan	-33%	-31%	-44%	-57%	20.2	2.9%	0.73	2067	1.12	3.1%
7	Indonesia	490%	50%	-7%	-86%	13.6	1.9%	0.73	2043	0.64	1.7%
8	Iran	297%	16%	-30%	-86%	12.8	1.8%	0.80	2044	0.71	1.9%
9	South Korea	114%	-15%	-29%	-55%	11.5	1.7%	0.61	2054	0.65	1.8%
10	Canada	39%	1%	-21%	-66%	10.6	1.5%	0.64	2048	0.61	1.7%
11	Brazil	138%	15%	0%	-45%	10.2	1.5%	0.47	2051	0.47	1.3%
12	Saudi Arabia	293%	18%	-33%	-91%	10.1	1.4%	0.66	2043	0.58	1.6%
13	Mexico	61%	-6%	-19%	-46%	9.7	1.4%	0.45	2055	0.49	1.3%
14	South Africa	58%	4%	-15%	-62%	8.6	1.2%	0.51	2048	0.48	1.3%
15	Türkiye	225%	22%	-18%	-80%	7.8	1.1%	0.46	2045	0.41	1.1%
16	Australia	44%	-2%	-23%	-65%	7.1	1.0%	0.42	2049	0.41	1.1%
17	UK	-61%	-37%	-49%	-60%	6.7	1.0%	0.13	2081	0.36	1.0%
18	Viet Nam	2786%	76%	-54%	-102%	6.7	1.0%	0.42	2039	0.34	0.9%
19	Pakistan	169%	-11%	-23%	-34%	5.6	0.8%	0.08	2080	0.20	0.5%
20	Thailand	238%	13%	-8%	-61%	5.5	0.8%	0.30	2048	0.29	0.8%
21	Taiwan	101%	-9%	-28%	-60%	5.1	0.7%	0.28	2051	0.29	0.8%
22	Egypt	294%	52%	-7%	-88%	5.1	0.7%	0.27	2043	0.24	0.6%
23	Malaysia	426%	33%	-34%	-95%	4.6	0.7%	0.30	2042	0.26	0.7%
24	Nigeria	127%	35%	49%	31%	4.3	0.6%	0.11	2058	0.13	0.3%
25	Ukraine	-87%	-52%	-58%	-64%	4.0	0.6%	0.00	2099	0.21	0.6%
26	Kazakhstan	2%	16%	-35%	-89%	3.9	0.6%	0.25	2043	0.22	0.6%
27	Iraq	257%	28%	-25%	-88%	3.7	0.5%	0.22	2043	0.19	0.5%
28	Bangladesh	959%	43%	51%	23%	3.7	0.5%	0.10	2057	0.11	0.3%
29	Philippines	465%	63%	32%	-63%	3.7	0.5%	0.17	2045	0.15	0.4%
30	Argentina	46%	-20%	-36%	-53%	3.6	0.5%	0.13	2063	0.18	0.5%
31	Algeria	122%	-12%	-29%	-52%	3.5	0.5%	0.15	2057	0.18	0.5%
32	Un. Arab Em.	304%	16%	-26%	-86%	3.4	0.5%	0.23	2044	0.20	0.5%
33	Venezuela	-7%	-21%	-26%	-39%	2.4	0.3%	0.09	2062	0.12	0.3%
34	Uzbekistan	65%	83%	-71%	-102%	2.3	0.3%	0.14	2038	0.12	0.3%
35	Qatar	788%	28%	-45%	-98%	2.0	0.3%	0.14	2041	0.12	0.3%
sum						646	92.5%	34.8		34.6	94.2%
other countries						52	8%			2.1	6%
global budget distributed here						698	100%			36.7	100%

Table 1: National CO2 budgets and reduction targets for the 35 largest resulting CO2 budgets

These 35 countries are responsible for 94% of the global CO2 emissions considered here in 2019 and would receive 93% of the global CO2 budget distributed under the selected global framework

data. These countries would have to achieve net negative CO₂ emissions at the national level, resulting in a cumulative total of 34.8 Gt, whereas they emitted 34.6 Gt in 2019.

Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the emission pathways and the annual rates of change for the six largest emitters (with 2019–2024 representing actual values).

Figure 1: Emission pathways of the six largest emitters

Figure 2: Annual change rates of the six largest emitters

¹⁴ Calculations are based on the tool presented and made available for download [in](#) (Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2026).

Abnormalities in Table 1: Early neutrality years for Vietnam and Uzbekistan are driven by sharp emission increases in 2024 (+10% and +12%), while the later neutrality year for Ukraine reflects a sharp decline in emissions (-39% in 2024 relative to 2021).

4 Reconciliation with the submitted NDCs (implicit CO2 budgets)

Implicit CO2 budgets can be derived from the submitted NDCs using simplified assumptions. See this web application for more information: <https://IB-IWP.climate-calculator.info>.

The following results were obtained for the six largest emitters:

country	implicit budget (NDC) in Gt	budget according to Table 1 in Gt	deviation	deviation in %
China	332	213	119	56%
United States	73	87	-14	-16%
EU27	42	54	-12	-22%
India	91	58	33	58%
Russia	45	33	12	38%
Japan	17	20	-3	-16%
sum	600	464	136	29%

Table 2: Comparison with the implicit CO2 budgets of the six largest emitters

In the present framework, the six largest emitters would receive 67% (464 Gt) of the remaining global CO2 budget (698 Gt), whereas in 2019 they were responsible for 69% of global emissions and accounted for 50% of the global population. Based on the implicit CO2 budgets, they would take up 86% (600 Gt) of the global CO2 budget.

Within the global framework data applied here, the EU provides an illustrative example: by submitting an NDC that implies a cumulative CO2 budget of about 42 Gt — well below the 54 Gt derived from the global framework data used here — the EU effectively leaves around 12 Gt of the remaining global CO2 budget unused. In accounting terms, this budget becomes implicitly available to other countries, even though no explicit transfer via Article 6 mechanisms of the Paris Agreement takes place.

Assuming full implementation of the submitted NDCs, and based on the simplified assumptions used here to derive implicit cumulative CO2 budgets, the six largest emitters have a net remaining gap of 136 Gt within the framework applied here. This figure is already a net figure for the six largest emitters: the implicit under-use of the budgets by the United States, the EU and Japan is offset against the excess implicit budgets of China, India and Russia. The remaining gap could therefore be reduced either by higher ambition in countries whose NDCs imply budgets above their allocated budgets, or by additional under-use of allocated budgets in other countries, including through further mitigation, provided that this additional budget space is interpreted as an implicit or explicit budget transfer. To the extent that the remaining net gap is not closed in either of these ways, it would require additional net negative CO2 emissions by 2100 to compensate for the resulting temporary overshoot in the sense used here. This value should therefore not be interpreted as

the full real-world mitigation gap. It represents a conditional estimate of the net political ambition gap under the assumption of full NDC implementation. Any failure to meet the submitted NDCs would create an additional implementation gap.

5 Approaches to closing the mitigation gap

The analysis in Chapters 3 and 4 shows that, even under global framework data designed to make maximum use of the available leeway to arrive at feasible outcomes, the required emission pathways remain effectively unattainable for some countries under real-world political, economic, and technological constraints.¹⁵ In particular, it appears unlikely that China, the largest emitter, and India, the fourth largest emitter, could reach CO₂ emissions neutrality by 2047 and 2045, respectively (see Table 1).

Moreover, a substantial discrepancy exists between the emission budgets derived from the global framework and the targets currently reflected in the NDCs of the six largest emitters (see Table 2).

These findings indicate that closing the mitigation gap requires a differentiated approach. The shortfall cannot be attributed to a single cause but consists of structurally distinct components requiring different policy responses.

This chapter therefore proceeds in two analytical steps. First, Chapter 5.1 develops a conceptualization of the mitigation gap. Second, Chapters 5.2–5.4 discuss potential approaches to addressing the main components of this gap, focusing on increased political ambition, international budget transfers, and additional net negative CO₂ emissions.

¹⁵ Real-world political developments — such as the United States' second withdrawal from the Paris Agreement and Russia no longer considering itself bound by it — are not taken into account.

5.1 Conceptualization of the mitigation gap

In the present framework, the mitigation gap does not represent a single, homogeneous shortfall.

Rather, it can be analytically decomposed into several distinct components, which differ fundamentally in their causes and in the policy instruments available to address them.

Component	Comparison	Interpretation	Main policy response
Political ambition gap	NDC-implied budgets vs. Paris-compatible national budgets under the selected global framework data	Submitted targets are not sufficiently ambitious in cumulative budget terms	Strengthened NDCs, tighter domestic targets, enhanced international cooperation
Implementation gap	Actual or projected emissions vs. NDC-implied pathways	NDC-implied pathways are not attained in practice	Credible policy instruments, binding emissions caps in emissions trading systems, investment frameworks, monitoring and enforcement
Structural feasibility gap	Paris-compatible national pathways vs. realistically attainable domestic mitigation pathways	Paris-compatible national pathways derived under the selected framework data may be effectively unattainable under real-world constraints	Budget transfers, technology cooperation, finance, burden-sharing mechanisms; see residual gap
Residual gap	Remaining excess emissions after feasible ambition increases, implementation, and transfers	Part of the gap cannot plausibly be closed through domestic mitigation alone	Additional net negative CO ₂ emissions; coordinated CDR institutions

Box 1: Analytical components of the mitigation gap

Political ambition gap

This component reflects the difference between the emission pathways implied by currently submitted NDCs and the national CO₂ budgets derived from the global framework data used in this paper. In principle, this gap is politically addressable through strengthened targets, revised policies, and increased international cooperation.

Implementation gap

This component reflects the difference between actual or projected emissions and the emission pathways implied by submitted NDCs.¹⁶ It is not quantified in this paper, because the comparison in Chapter 4 is based on the simplifying assumption that submitted NDCs are fully implemented. If actual emissions exceed NDC-implied pathways, this implementation gap arises in addition to the political ambition gap and increases the overall mitigation challenge.

¹⁶ Submitted NDCs may themselves be based on overly optimistic assumptions regarding technological deployment, infrastructure expansion, policy implementation, or political stability. In such cases, an implementation gap may arise not only from insufficient execution, but also from the limited real-world attainability of the NDC-implied pathway.

Structural feasibility gap

For several countries, the budgets shown in Table 1 imply emission pathways that appear to require faster or deeper domestic emission reductions than can realistically be achieved under the global framework data applied here. These countries face structural constraints related to economic development, technological readiness, infrastructure turnover, and political stability. This component of the mitigation gap reflects binding limits to the speed and depth of domestic mitigation under real-world conditions.

Unlike the political ambition gap, the structural feasibility gap is not primarily an accounting gap. It refers to cases in which Paris-compatible budgets derived under the selected framework data imply emission pathways that are effectively unattainable under real-world political, economic, and technological constraints.

Residual gap

After accounting for realistic increases in ambition, credible implementation of realistically attainable NDC-implied pathways, feasible domestic mitigation, and realistic international budget transfers, a residual gap may remain for some major emitters.

This gap cannot plausibly be closed through national mitigation efforts alone. One possible response would be to complement feasible domestic mitigation and realistic budget transfers with additional mechanisms, such as collectively organized net negative CO₂ emissions.

5.2 Increased ambition

The remaining mitigation gap suggests that further increases in ambition would be important wherever they are realistically achievable. Within the framework applied here, countries whose NDCs imply cumulative CO₂ budgets (see Table 2) significantly above those derived from the global framework data (see Table 1) would be particularly relevant cases for considering strengthened targets.

5.3 Budget transfers between countries

A fundamental question is whether transferring budget space under the global framework data selected here could substantially reduce the remaining gap. An indicator of the potential for a budget transfer could be the year of emissions neutrality in Table 1.

In this context, transferable budget space does not arise automatically. It exists only if a country's implicit budget remains below the budget allocated to it under the framework used here, or if a country increases its ambition beyond that level. Without such unused budget space, a transfer would merely reallocate accounting rights without reducing the remaining global mitigation gap.

One possible guideline could be:

- Countries whose allocated budgets under this framework imply comparatively late CO₂ emissions neutrality years may have potential transferable budget space, provided that this space is also reflected in an NDC or in additional mitigation beyond the NDC.¹⁷
- Countries that would have to reach CO₂ emissions neutrality well before 2050 and are not among the very rich countries would likely require additional budget space.

However, Table 1 indicates that the potential volume of transferable budget space from countries with comparatively late neutrality years is too small to offset the additional budget requirements of major emitters facing very early neutrality constraints.

With regard to market- and cooperation-based mechanisms under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement, it should be noted that, since current NDCs are not collectively Paris-compatible under the framework applied here, it would generally be necessary for a country to **tighten its NDC** accordingly when it transfers mitigation outcomes or budget space. Otherwise, there would be no additional global benefit, except perhaps greater cost efficiency or fairer burden sharing.¹⁸

5.4 Closing the residual gap

5.4.1 UN agency for negative CO₂ emissions

Even if NDCs are strengthened where feasible, implemented credibly, and complemented by globally effective budget transfers based on additional unused budget space, these measures may still prove insufficient to achieve the temperature objective of the Paris Agreement.

One option for addressing the residual gap would be additional negative CO₂ emissions¹⁹, which would be pre-financed and, under certain circumstances, also implemented by an agency to be established under the umbrella of the UN.

As a first step, all countries could contribute to the financing in accordance with their economic capacity, for example measured by gross national income (GNI). However, this is only pre-financing. The agency would only implement negative CO₂ emissions commissioned by countries. These countries would repay the costs incurred in this process through long-term installments. Per capita

¹⁷ Of the six largest emitters, the United States, the EU and Japan already implicitly provide such scope, at least in part, by submitting NDCs whose implicit CO₂ budgets fall below the budgets resulting from the global framework data applied here (cf. Chapter 4 Reconciliation with the submitted NDCs (implicit CO₂ budgets)).

¹⁸ See also the relevant **excursus** [in](#) (Sargl, et al., 2026).

¹⁹ This requires the **permanent** removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere, commonly referred to as carbon dioxide removal (CDR), including approaches such as BECCS, DACCS, and other forms of carbon dioxide removal, provided that the removed CO₂ is stored permanently.

income can be taken into account when determining installment amounts and repayment periods, so that poorer countries are not overburdened.

It should be emphasized that such additional negative CO₂ emissions would be required if any remaining net gap that cannot be closed through stronger NDCs, credible implementation, domestic mitigation, or feasible budget transfers is to be compensated. This includes, but is not limited to, the net gap identified in Chapter 4; it may also include additional gaps arising from the non-fulfillment of submitted NDCs. These removals would be additional to the national net negative emissions already included in the reference pathways to offset the temporary overshoots shown in Table 1, and additional to removals needed to offset other unavoidable greenhouse gases.

These negative CO₂ emissions should be implemented in such a way that any resulting additional global overshoot remains below a level that would entail unacceptable risks in terms of tipping points in the climate system and damage caused by temporarily exceeding the temperature target. To this end, it would be helpful to implement these negative CO₂ emissions as quickly as possible. However, this must not compromise the reduction of positive CO₂ emissions.

Such an agency would not substitute for rapid reductions in positive CO₂ emissions. However, if implemented early and at sufficient scale, it could help address a remaining net gap and reduce the risk and magnitude of additional temporary overshoot. Other institutional arrangements for achieving the necessary negative CO₂ emissions are also conceivable.

5.4.2 Assessment of the challenge of negative CO₂ emissions

Achieving such volumes of negative CO₂ emissions would represent a major challenge. One possible technological approach is direct air capture with carbon storage (DACCS).

Table 3 provides an illustrative scaling exercise. It proportionally scales the net NDC ambition gap identified for the six largest emitters (cf. Chapter 4) to the global level and assumes DACCS costs of 150 USD per tonne of CO₂. Under these assumptions, total removal expenditures would amount to approximately #30 trillion USD. This corresponds to about #17% of global gross domestic product (GDP) in 2024.²⁰ Distributed evenly over a period of 20 years, this would amount to roughly #1% of annual global GDP.

The annual energy requirement relative to global primary energy demand in 2023 may exceed 10%. Such high additional electricity demand would require a substantial expansion of low-carbon energy

²⁰ The actual gap would be larger if the NDCs are not met and could potentially be smaller if the NDCs are strengthened.

supply, which may entail significant land-use and infrastructure implications, depending on the generation mix.

Net NDC ambition gap, six largest emitters (see Table 2)	136 Gt
Share of the six largest emitters in global emissions, 2019	69%
Proportionally scaled global ambition gap	197 Gt
DACCS cost input	\$150 / t
Total DACCS costs	\$29.6 trillion
Global GDP 2024 (derived from EDGAR country data)	\$173 trillion
Share of total DACCS costs in global GDP in 2024	17%
Cost allocation period	20 years
Annual DACCS costs	\$1.5 trillion
Share of annual DACCS costs in global GDP in 2024	0.9%
Global primary energy consumption in 2023 (PEC)	176.0 thousand TWh
Energy demand per tonne of CO ₂ removed	2.0 MWh
Total DACCS energy consumption	394.2 thousand TWh
Annual DACCS energy consumption	19.7 thousand TWh
Share of annual DACCS energy demand in global PEC in 2023	11.2%

Table 3: Illustrative costs and energy consumption of compensating the gap using DACCS

These estimates can be verified and replicated using the tool referenced below, where key parameters — including removal volumes, cost assumptions, and energy intensity — can be adjusted: <https://DACCS.climate-calculator.info>.

6 Conclusion

This paper examined whether territorially defined national emission targets can remain collectively compatible with the Paris Agreement under a set of global framework data designed to avoid overly optimistic assumptions regarding emission reductions, land-use change, and the availability of negative emissions.

The analysis shows that even under such conditions a mitigation gap remains. This gap consists of several structurally different components: a political ambition gap between current NDCs and Paris-compatible emission budgets, an implementation gap between NDC-implied pathways and actual or projected emissions, a structural feasibility gap reflecting limits to the speed and depth of domestic decarbonization, and a residual gap that cannot plausibly be closed through national mitigation efforts alone.

Addressing these components requires a combination of policy responses. Strengthened national climate policies and more ambitious NDCs remain indispensable. International cooperation — including budget transfers or other burden-sharing mechanisms — may help alleviate distributional tensions. However, the analysis also indicates that these measures alone may prove insufficient.

If a residual mitigation gap remains despite strengthened NDCs, credible implementation, feasible domestic mitigation, and realistic budget transfers, large-scale carbon dioxide removal may become necessary to preserve collective Paris compatibility and limit the risks associated with temporary overshoot. One possible institutional approach discussed in this paper is the establishment of an international agency for negative CO₂ emissions that could coordinate large-scale removal activities and enable collective financing of the associated costs, thereby helping to address coordination failures in the provision of carbon dioxide removal as a global public good.

In this sense, the framework presented here should be understood as a feasibility stress test for collectively Paris-compatible national targets rather than as a prescriptive allocation of the remaining global CO₂ budget, illustrating the magnitude of the remaining mitigation challenge under realistic global boundary conditions.

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